

CUMULATIVE DAMAGE PROBLEM IN PULL-THROUGH FATIGUE OF C.F.R.P. LAMINATE

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ABSTRACT

The pull-through fatigue behaviour of CFRP laminate is an important design consideration. Up to now only a few papers concerning the static pull-through tests have been published. The present paper, the authors believe, describes the pull-through fatigue test and investigates the development of fatigue damage for the first time. Environmental effect is also considered.

Self-designed testing fixture possesses many advantages, such as, easy and simple installation, good simulation of the actual load, prevention of eccentricity, etc. An important contribution of this paper is that the residual stiffness theory⁵ (Please see the section on Cumulative Damage Problem) is creatively adapted to deal with pull-through fatigue behaviour, "Damage parameter" and "Damage Point" are defined for the first time based on the experimental data or curves.

INTRODUCTION

Carbon fibre reinforced plastics (CFRP) have found a wide use as an ideal material in aircraft structures. The pull-through fatigue behaviour of CFRP laminate should become an important design problem for engineers. Mechanical fasteners, often used to join the wing skin to other components, may be pulled through the plate by a large through plane shear force which is transformed by the aerodynamic load q . A typical pull-through mode was shown in Fig.1. It is apparent that the total loads applied to the plate include not only the pull force but also the bending moment. Especially, the damage may often initiate and propagate in the fastened region of composites during service. Hence the final damage state which precedes the sudden failure can be observed. It is important that the pull-through fatigue damage must be accurately estimated to perform the fatigue design with safety and reliability.

EXPERIMENT

(1) Specimens -- All specimens were made from T300/648 CFRP with stacking sequence $(0/\pm 45)_s$. The geometry of pull-through specimen is shown in Fig.2. Two environmental conditions, "dry" or "wet" are considered; for the former approach the specimens are into dried container with silica gel over 30hr and for the latter, the specimens are dipped into water of 20°C over one week after having been dried. The weight of specimen was measured at regular intervals.

(2) Device and Fixture--The schematic diagram of self-designed testing device and fixture are shown as Fig.3. They possess the following advantages: A. It is easy and simple to be installed. B. In order to avoid buckling and eccentricity effects, the compressive rod cross section is designed strong enough and the axis is ensured to coincide with the

loading axis. C. The pull-through fixture base is provided with three rabbets with different diameters in order to satisfy the requirements of different loading cases. D. This fixture can simulate well the real pull-through load.

Both static and fatigue tests were conducted at the MTS 810 hydraulic servo testing system.

(3) Test Results -- A. Static Test -- The load/deflection plots (p-w curves) are drawn automatically. Under dry and wet conditions, p-w curves are shown in Fig.4. The first step in the plot was defined damage load (P_d) or the first crackle load, and the maximum load (P_{max}) means entirely failure. $P_d \approx 70\%P_{max}$. Comparing the average of the above two conditions, we get $(P_{max})_{wet} \approx 80\%(P_{max})_{dry}$. Obviously the environmental effect is important for the joint of composite material. B. Fatigue Test Results -- Under room-temperature and dry condition, compression-compression ($R=0$) constant amplitude ($P_f \approx 0.7P_d$) fatigue tests at 4-5 Hz are performed and the hysteresis loop curves are drawn, as shown in Fig.5 (a). Its area is proportional to the dissipated energy per cycle. The slope of the top part of the p-w curve represents the stiffness. Obviously, the slope may be changed with cyclic numbers. The number of cycles (n), at which the load drops due to the damage propagation in the specimen, is taken as the life ($n=N$) of the specimen at the certain load level. The same fatigue tests for wet specimen were also conducted and its hysteresis loop of pull-through fatigue was shown in Fig. 5(b). Comparing two different environmental conditions wet specimen is usually much weaker than the dry one. C. Statistical Analysis -- Because the defects of laminate including void, delamination, small cracks, looseness of structure and inhomogeneity of resin etc. were usually detected, the fatigue test data have larger scatter. From the statistical point of view for this problem, the test data is treated, the calculation and analysis see other paper[6]. The deflection increment is Δw and the slope $\tan \alpha = P_{max}/W=r$ is the stiffness, the relation of $N-\Delta w$ and $N=\tan \alpha$ curves are shown respectively in Figs. 6. and 7.

CUMULATIVE DAMAGE PROBLEM

The cumulative damage (CD) problem is formulated in terms of a damage function which must satisfy certain conditions. A major difference between metals and composite materials is that fatigue failure in fiber composite laminates occurs as a result of accumulation of many cracks, rather than by the propagation of one dominant crack, and these cracks are not easily detected.

There are three cumulative damage theories:

(1) Residual strength theory

Suppose the specimen is cycled for n cycles at constant amplitude P for $R=0$ fatigue test, the specimen is removed from the testing machine and is subjected to a static failure test. The static strength thus obtained, it is defined as the residual strength load P_r . $P_r < P_0$ (the initial static strength load).

The simplest form of the damage function is

$$D = \frac{P_0 - P_r}{P_0} = 1 - \frac{P_r}{P_0} \quad (1)$$

when $P_r=0$, then $D=1$, failure is identified; when $P_r=P_0$, then $D=0$ the residual strength is equal to static strength that means no damage.

(2) Residual life theory -- Hashin shown that it is completely equivalent with the residual strength C.D theory.

(3) Residual stiffness theory -- Wang and Chim's theory is only applicable to study the fatigue property of materials, the damage function is

$$D = 1 - E_i/E_0 \quad (2)$$

where E_i is the residual Young's Moduli of i cycles and E_0 is the static test Young's Moduli. Then $E_i < E_0$

Now we introduce a new stiffness parameter

$$r_i = P_i/W_i \quad (3)$$

where $P_i = P_0$ -- cyclic load amplitude

W_i = resultant deflection after i cycles

Then the damage function of pull-through joint may be shown as

$$D = 1 - \frac{r_i}{r_0} = 1 - W_0/W_i \quad (4)$$

When $W_i=W_0$, $D=0$ that means no damage, when $W_i \gg W_0$, $D=1$, that means failure is identified, r_i and r_0 can be determined by hysteresis loop in the pull-through fatigue test as shown in Figs. 6 and 7. The values of r_i and r_0 so determined are listed tabulated in Table I.

According to the residual stiffness theory, D can be computed by Eq. 2. and plotting data of various specimen are shown in Fig.8. It can be seen from Table I, when $D=0.4$ the specimen would start damage, but it would not completely lose the load carrying capability. When $D=0.5$, the slope of curve would change rapidly. This point named accumulate damage limit point (d.p)-- as yield point of steel was a standard limit of strength, D should be less than 0.5.

Damage and Mechanism -- Pull-through fatigue is different from the other damage, such as bearing, tension or compression damage, in which the load is perpendicular to all fibers and the maximum loads are distributed around the hole at the contact points. The damaged specimens were detected and analysed by TBE radiograph prints and SEM analysis. Fig.9 presents X-ray photographs in no loaded specimen and only some mechanical damage exists. Fig.10 shows X-ray photographs of pull-through fatigue at the final damage state (FDS). When $n=5860$ cycles first crack sound is heard, the matrix cracking and pull-through delamination occur as shown in the dark-shadow area around the pull hole. Other general photographs were shown in Fig.11. (a) pull-through typical form (b) bottom of the specimen side view, delamination and broken fibers. Photographs of pull-through specimen around the hole surface at the final damage state (FDS) from scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was shown in Fig.12. (a) matrix cracks on the step station around the pull hole, and growing delamination between the interface (488X) (b) fiber debonding beside the hole (1000X)

CONCLUSIONS

- (1) The strength and stiffness in pull-through fatigue of CFRP laminate under wet condition was decreased significantly.
- (2) The pull-through fatigue life of limit damage point (d.p) was corresponding to its critical strength.
- (3) The slope of the load-deflection curve would decrease due to accumulate damage with the numbers of fatigue cycles increased.
- (4) Various diameter or fastener hole of CFRP laminate would have different pull-through fatigue strength and the larger hole should increase the strength.
- (5) Accumulated damage was start with the tension surface of the specimen, and the crack extent from outside towards inside of the laminate, at last cycle pull-through failure occurs.

(6) Delaminations are parallel to the fiber direction in each ply. The damage mechanism of the CFRP joints is very complex, but it is possible to follow its evolution by measuring the following parameters:
 -- The total stiffness and hysteresis loop.

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Table I Comparison of pull-through accumulated damage under dry and wet condition

(a) d=6mm						(b) d=5mm						
No. of Specimen	N	r _i	r _o	r _i /r _o	D	No. of Specimen	N	r _i	r _o	r _i /r _o	D	
1-17 (dry)	1	1.66	1.66	1.00	0.00	0-6 (dry)	1	1.66	1.66	1.00	0.00	
	7000	1.66	1.66	1.00	0.00		4000	1.54	1.66	0.93	0.07	
	19000	1.54	1.66	0.93	0.07		5500	1.25	1.66	0.75	0.25	
	23000	1.54	1.66	0.93	0.07		5860	0.56	1.66	0.34	0.66	
	24000	1.34	1.66	0.8	0.20							
	25000	1.00	1.66	0.6	0.40							
1'-9 (wet)	1	1.66	1.66	1.00	0	0'-26 (wet)	1	1.66	1.66	1.00	0.00	
	5000	1.66	1.66	1.00	0		1500	1.66	1.66	1.00	0.00	
	11000	1.66	1.66	1.00	0		2000	1.66	1.66	1.00	0.00	
	13000	1.43	1.66	0.84	0.14		3000	1.54	1.66	0.93	0.07	
	13100	1.00	1.66	0.60	0.40		4000	1.41	1.66	0.87	0.13	
	15000	0.62	1.66	0.37	0.63		4740	1.25	1.66	0.75	0.25	
					5000	1.11	1.66	0.67	0.33			
					5500	1.00	1.66	0.60	0.40			

Fig.1 Mode of failure for pull-through in the skin of aerofoil

Fig.2. Pull-through specimen
 a -length=30—36mm
 b = a -width
 d -inside hole diameter=5—6mm
 t -thickness=3.3mm
 D -Outside hole diameter=8mm

Fig.3. The self-designed testing device

- 1.washer plate
- 2.deflection transducer
- 3.pull-through fixture base
- 4.specimen
- 5.compression rod (detecting head)
- 6.maximum cylindrical support
- 7.median cylindrical support
- 8.minmum cylindrical support
- 9.guide rod
- 10.upper clip

Fig.4. Static pull-through test p-w curves

a. $d=5\text{mm}$

b. $d=6\text{mm}$

Fig.5. The hysteresis loop changes during pull-through fatigue, p-w curves

Fig.6. $N-\Delta w$ curves

Fig.7. $N-tg\alpha$ curves

b. $d=6\text{mm}$

a. $d=5\text{mm}$

Fig.8. Damage parameter D changes during the fatigue with increasing the cycles number

Fig.9. x-ray potographs of specimens at no load state

Fig.10. x-ray potographs of pull-through fatigue specimens the final damage state (FDS)

Fig.11. The photographs of pull-through failure

Fig.12. Scanning electron micrograph of pull-through fatigue specimens at the final damage state.